

Feasibility Assessment Dimensions		
	Assessment	Justification
Existing Infrastructure <i>(Inadequate, Sufficient, Complete)</i>		
Legislative framework and regulation <i>(Inadequate, With Shortcomings, Sufficient)</i>		
IT literacy of PS employees, citizens, businesses <i>(Low, Moderate, High)</i>		
Political Will <i>(Inadequate commitment, Strong commitment)</i>		

SONNETS